

LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GENDER- EXPRESSIVE PROVERBS IN TOGAY MURAD'S STORIES

Xolmirzayeva Latofat Abdullayevna

Graduate student of Alfraganus University

Abstract. This article studies the gender characteristics of proverbs used in the stories of Togay Murad, a rare connoisseur of our mentality, from a linguistic and cultural perspective. The national and cultural aspects of the proverbs used in the stories are revealed. The writer's skillful use of folk proverbs and the skill of creating individual proverbs based on them are also shown.

Keywords: proverb, , gender, paremiology, linguistic and cultural studies.

INTRODUCTION.

Today's modern era also imposes certain requirements on Uzbek linguistics. In the era of globalization, the study of language and its application in practice, strengthening the connection between languages through various effective methods are the main goals of linguistics.

A person begins his life with a gender characteristic. Therefore, when a baby is born, he is greeted with pink clothes and diapers if it is a girl, and blue clothes and diapers if it is a boy. Those who come to the maternity hospital to see the baby ask whether it is a boy or a girl to determine the gender characteristic. However, gender is not a biological sex or sexual characteristic. This difference is considered very important in understanding the extent to which our views on biological sex affect gender characteristic¹.

The role of women or men in society is largely determined by cultural

¹ Usmanova Sh. Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik. – Toshkent: "BOOKMANY PRINT" – B.222.

perceptions. For example, some activities are characterized as more masculine or more feminine. Thus, whether people hunt or sew, fight or recite poetry may differ from what others think of them. The television shows, TV series, football matches, etc, that people watch affect how they interact with others in gendered contexts².

So far, a number of studies have been carried out in Uzbek linguistics devoted to the linguo-cultural characteristics of the language. Nevertheless, the linguo-cultural analysis of a work of art still remains a relevant issue. Therefore, the inclusion of gender lexis, in particular proverbs, in the stories of Togay Murod, a rare connoisseur of our mentality, in the linguo-cultural analysis is of great importance.

In Uzbek linguistics, the recent years, namely the period of the revival of national values, require the speaker to deeply master the language, especially the Uzbek literary language, which has the status of the state language; to express the thought concisely, reasonably, figuratively and impressively. There are poets and writers, orators and eloquent, old and young, who, if they want to substantiate or strengthen the thought being expressed, will certainly turn to proverbs. From a pragmatic point of view, proverbs can be used, among other things, to scold, console, instruct, advise, teach, warn, threaten. But not every proverb and saying is a subject of linguistic and cultural research. In this case, only proverbs and sayings that are closely related to the history, culture, life, spirituality, etc. of a particular people or ethnic group should be studied.

In some places in linguistics, the concepts of proverb and idiom are distinguished. Idioms are words or combinations of words whose meaning does not depend on the original meaning of the lexical units in their composition, but give a

² Judith Martin, Thomas Nakayama. Intercultural communication in contexts. - 5th ed. -New York: McGraw-Hill, 2010. -P. 180-181.

single, unified meaning³. According to its structure, an idiom can consist of a word, a phrase, or a sentence. Words whose meaning does not depend on the original meaning of the lexical units in their composition are idioms: *suyuqoyoq* – a whore (“There was a saying in the country that Munavvar was a “*suyuqoyoq*” woman.”)⁴

We can also see the phenomenon of a statement about an individual situation becoming a proverb in the proverb (*Qirqiga chidagan, qirq biriga ham chidaydi*) "He who endures forty, endures forty-one"⁵ used in the work "Oydinda yurgan odamlar". This proverb is used with great skill by Togay Murad in the work in the scene where the bride is asked for her consent to the wedding, which is one of the beautiful traditions of the Uzbek people, and the bride remains silent and the groom becomes disappointed when the time passes.

In the story "Ot kishnagan oqshom", Togay Murad found a unique way to use folk proverbs. This proverb glorifies courage. The courage of a brave man is especially emphasized. With this proverb, you will not feel sorry if a brave man eats your soup, because a brave man deserves such respect. The phrase "*Boshingni yesa-da, mard yesin!*" means that even if he kills you, a brave man should kill you. First of all, it is said that a brave man kills once, and a coward kills a thousand times. Therefore, a person who dies at the hands of a brave man does not feel sorry for his death. After all, dying at the hands of a brave man is also an honor. By using

³ { 3,26} Jo'rayeva G.H.Tog'ay Murod qissalaridagi ayrim lingvokulteremalarning lingvomadaniy tahlili.//XX asr tilshunosligi:tahlil va talqin, -№ 4. —Navoiy,2023 —B.61.

⁴ { 4.82} Jo'rayeva G.H.Tog'ay Murod qissalaridagi ayrim lingvokulteremalarning lingvomadaniy tahlili.// XX asr tilshunosligi:tahlil va talqin, -№ 4. —Navoiy,2023. —B.61.

⁵ { 4,19} Jo'rayeva G.H.Tog'ay Murod qissalaridagi ayrim lingvokulteremalarning lingvomadaniy tahlili.// XX asr tilshunosligi:tahlil va talqin ,№ 4. — Navoiy,2023. —B.61.

this proverb, the writer promotes universal human values that a man should be brave and courageous.

*Birodarlar, o‘zbek eli o‘r keladi, o‘zi o‘jar, zo‘r keladi!*⁶ (translation: Brothers, the Uzbek people are stubborn).

This proverb used by Togay Murad expresses the Uzbek nation, its character, agility, and bravery. There are no superfluous words in this figurative expression, each word is used clearly and in its place, the words “o‘r”, “o‘jar”, “zo‘r” rhyme with each other. The repetition of the word “keladi” provides the melody of the proverb, creating a unique rhythm. Since ancient times, Uzbek young men have been recognized for their handsome appearance, eloquence, courage, and bravery. This proverb also expresses the qualities of masculinity.

As is known, proverbs embody the wisdom of the working people, national traditions, centuries-old life experiences, thoughts, arguments, and labor about natural and social phenomena. That is why proverbs are long-lived. Each historical period, socio-political events have left their mark on proverbs to some extent. Also, new proverbs are created, enriching the treasury of word art.

Perhaps it is not surprising that Togay Murad's interest in folklore traditions was born when he was a farmer, watering the vast fields side by side with the watermen, in the company of yilqibakars and polvans, and at weddings. Therefore, proverbs with deep and broad meaning, instructive, and expressing complete thoughts were embedded in the works of Togay Murad. Proverbs served to ensure the expressiveness of the speeches of the heroes of the work. In particular:

“Bir kalning hiylasi - qirq kishini charchatadi”⁷ (translation: "One bald man's trick can tire out forty men). In folk tales, the bald man is depicted as a cunning and

⁶ Тоғай Мурод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.:Шарқ , 1994. – Б. 129.

⁷ Тоғай Мурод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.:Шарқ , 1994. – Б. 154.

cunning person. In the story "Ot kishnagan oqshom" Togay Murad likens the man sent as a representative from Moscow to that cunning and spotted bald man. Indeed, representatives from Moscow in those times would fool everyone, just like the bald man in the fairy tales.

“Erkak odamning yig‘lagani – o‘lgani.”⁸(translation: A man's crying is a death). Proverbs discuss courage, the fact that a man is the pillar of the family, and his honor. However, the bald man described in this proverb, used in the story of Togay Murad, is not such a powerful man. When a representative from Moscow tries to remove him from his post and expel him from the party, the official cries bitterly. Feeling sorry for this, the proverb “Erkak odamning yig‘lagani – o‘lgani” is used in relation to the official who cries while being a man. Indeed, such a man who cries while being a man is not good. It is good that he died because he raised his head in this world saying “I am a man.” By using this proverb, the author once again emphasizes to the reader that the main character of the work, Ziyodulla Kal, is a true brave man, and is a sign of glorifying his human qualities.

“O‘zing yaxshi – olam yaxshi, o‘zing yomon – olam yomon”⁹(translation: If you are good, the world is good, if you are bad, the world is bad). In this proverb, steeped in wisdom, the writer describes a bald man, a former elder, lying in a teahouse and saying, "There is no truth, there is no truth in this world," and the idea is put forward that "If you were good, the world would be good, but because of your own badness, the world now looks bad to you." Of course, the fate of such people is bound to be a dream for the people, meaning that people will laugh at them. “Elga ermak, xalqqa shaloq”¹⁰(translation: Fun for the people,

⁸ Тоғай Мурод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.:Шарқ , 1994 –Б.154.

⁹ Тоғай Мурод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.: Шарқ , 1994. –Б.154.

¹⁰Тоғай Мурод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.: Шарқ , 1994 . – Б..154.

a disgrace to the people), the proverb was used for this very purpose. Because of this, the former leader is now everyone's laughing stock. The writer describes his tea drinking as follows: "The tea is white from the teapot. He pours it himself and drinks it himself." So, it is clear that now the people who are having fun are laughing at him sitting in the teahouse and drinking dirty water. Now the former leader is alone. No one drinks tea with him. Yes, it is very bad that he has lost his reputation.

Togay Murad's art of using proverbs is very high. We can also see his skill in using proverbs appropriately to increase the value of his work.

"Yon qo'shnim – jon qo'shnim"¹¹(translation: My next door neighbor is my soulmate). This proverb shows the usefulness of neighbors, their sympathy, support, and empathy for a person in good and bad times. The proverb glorifies neighborliness, friendship, alliance, and solidarity. Through this proverb, Togay Murad wants to show that our people have lived as neighbors since ancient times, how much they value their neighbors, and emphasize that they have lived by helping each other. In addition, he promotes universal human values.

"It is safe to say that he will leave his home - his deathbed - and move away from his relatives"¹². "Oydinda yurgan odamlar", the meaning of this proverb in the story is "It is better to sleep in a bed that is bare than in a soft bed in someone else's house or country." It emphasizes how valuable everyone's home and homeland are. The above proverb is also used in relation to a girl who is moving away from her home and getting married. The proverb talks about how valuable her home is for a

¹¹ Тоғай Мүрод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.: Шарқ , 1994. –Б.240.

¹² Тоғай Мүрод. От кишнаган оқшом. Қиссалар. – Т.: Шарқ , 1994 . –Б.240.

girl who is getting married, and how difficult it is for her to be away from her home.

Brothers, the prophets also honored the groom! Ahay-ahay! According to the narrations, our Prophet Muhammad honored his son-in-law Hazrat Ali. This proverb originated on this basis, and is said when honoring the groom or when teaching the need to honor him. There is also a proverb that says, "The groom has arrived - the khan has arrived," which expresses how much the father-in-law, mother-in-law, brother-in-law, brother-in-law, and in general, the people on the groom's side respect the groom, and when they cannot find a place to sit when he arrives, they honor him as if he were a khan.

CONCLUSION

The study of cultural signs in language is the fruit of the achievements of linguistics to date. The growing interest in linguocultural studies determines the future of the science. At the same time, the theoretical and methodological basis of the science is just being formed. In linguocultural studies, paremias, along with other linguocultural units, are studied as the main units reflecting cultural signs in language.

In the literature of the 20th century, the appeal to folklore traditions has become extremely strong in the work of Uzbek writers and poets. This can be seen in the works of Togay Murad. Togay Murad continued the traditions of our master writers and poets, such as Abdulla Qodiriy, Hamza, Oybek, Abdulla Qahhor, Gafur Ghulom, Hamid Olimjon and others, and followed his own unique ways of using folklore. That is why in the works of Togay Murad, the majestic spirit of the heroic epic, its exaggerated methods of depiction, and artistic means of depiction are more prominent than folklore plots, magical motifs of ancient legends and myths. We have examined this in particular in the stories of the writer "Yulduzlar mangu yonadi" and "Ot kishnagan oqshom". The writer is distinguished by his excellent

knowledge of proverbs, folk songs, alla, askiya, and anecdotes. With his works, Togay Murad proved in practice that examples of folk oral art never lose their significance and always acquire modernity due to the skill of the creator.

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